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URBAN LIGHTING FOR HEALTH & WELLBEING: NEW GUIDELINES

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33 A BETTER LIGHT FOR A GOOD QUALITY OF LIFE

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Urban lighting is a powerful tool for shaping health, wellbeing, and social life. However, cities still treat it as a technical matter, failing to unlock its full potential. The ENLIGHTENme project has proven that lighting affects sleep, safety, and social life, especially for vulnerable groups like older adults. Poorly designed lighting isolates people, undermining their possibility to improve their wellbeing and quality of life.

These Guidelines aim to change this by raising awareness among decision-makers about the importance of knowledge-based lighting policies. Departing from conventional practices, these Guidelines provide an opportunity to rethink urban planning and design, ensuring that lighting policies actively promote health and sustainability.

Built on insights from the ENLIGHTENme H2020 project, the Guidelines consolidate knowledge, research, and real-world evidence from pilot sites in Amsterdam, Bologna, and Tartu. These cities have served as living laboratories, helping to quantify the impact of lighting on human health, particularly among older adults—one of the most vulnerable groups to inappropriate light exposure. Poor lighting affects their ability to access public spaces, participate in civic life, and maintain overall wellbeing, making it a crucial factor in urban health strategies.

ENLIGHTENme's findings highlight the necessity of integrating lighting into broader urban policies, leveraging technological innovation, adaptive installations, and cross-sector collaboration. The Guidelines translate these insights into concrete, actionable recommendations, ensuring that lighting is no longer treated as an isolated issue but as a key element in designing people-centered cities.

The time for change is now. Cities must move beyond fragmented approaches and embrace lighting as a strategic asset for fostering healthier, more inclusive, and resilient urban environments.

Don Slater

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Leader of WP2: Co-created urban lighting interventions in the three ENLIGHTENme cities

Urban citizens have a complex but often subliminal relationship with light and the many roles it plays in the way public spaces are designed. You yourself will have experienced this every time a city space has made you feel insecure, excited, nostalgic, disabled, cosy, confused, efficient and so on. And the other people you share this space with – of different ages, genders, ethnicities – may experience that same lit space in radically other ways.

Cities cannot deal with the complex yet powerful role of lighting by treating it as a matter of technical standards or of creating pretty landscapes. These Guidelines propose, instead, a strategic approach to urban lighting that integrates it within wider policy and planning for citizens and seeks to deal with this complexity in an evidence-based and holistic way. These recommendations therefore do not take the form of specific lighting levels or measurements – lux or CCT levels that are good for everyone, everywhere – but rather ways of engaging with urban diversity and ensuring that city lighting design responds to the concerns of those who will actually use public spaces.

The Guidelines arose from the experience of ENLIGHTENme, which focused on how lighting can support the quality of life of older people in cities: two years of social research, community engagement and co-design, then engaging older citizens in exploring lighting through actual installations in their everyday spaces. This research programme made clear the range of different needs and concerns just within this one demographic, and pointed to the ways in which cities can try to connect lighting and urban design in an informed and ongoing way with urban life and diversity.

The result is a strategic approach that can be generalised to the city as a whole, to support the quality of life of all the diverse populations that share its public spaces.

Ms. Fatiha El Moudni

President of LUCI

Mayor of Rabat, Morocco

Cities are at the heart of human life. As hubs of culture, economy, and social interaction, they shape our daily experiences and influence our health and wellbeing. In this context, urban lighting plays a crucial yet often underappreciated role. It determines how we navigate our streets, how safe we feel in public spaces, and how connected we are to our communities. Thoughtful, inclusive lighting policies are essential to ensuring that cities remain vibrant, equitable, and welcoming for all.

The ENLIGHTENme project has reinforced the importance of integrating lighting into urban health and wellbeing strategies. This initiative has demonstrated that lighting is not merely a technical matter—it is a fundamental component of inclusive city planning. As the President of LUCI, the global network of cities dedicated to sustainable and people-centered urban lighting, I see firsthand how cities are rethinking their approach to lighting. No longer just a tool for visibility, lighting is becoming a means to promote public health, social inclusion, and sustainability.

From Rabat to Bologna, Amsterdam to Tartu, cities worldwide are facing common challenges: ageing populations, the need for safer public spaces, and the growing demand for energy-efficient infrastructure. The findings of ENLIGHTENme offer recommendations that help cities address these challenges through better lighting policies. By fostering collaboration between policymakers, urban planners, public health experts, and local communities, we can ensure that lighting strategies are holistic and responsive to the diverse needs of urban populations.

At LUCI, we believe that urban lighting should be people-centric. We advocate for lighting solutions that enhance accessibility, strengthen community engagement, and reduce inequalities in the built environment. These Guidelines mark an important step toward integrating lighting into broader urban policies, ensuring that cities of all sizes can create environments that support wellbeing, social interaction, and cultural vitality.

As we look to the future, cities must embrace lighting as a strategic asset—one that fosters more inclusive, resilient, and sustainable urban environments. The time to act is now. Through knowledge-sharing and collaboration, we can build cities where light is not only a tool for illumination but also a source of health, community, and quality of life.

WHO ARE

THESE GUIDELINES

FOR ?

The purpose of these Guidelines is to put health and wellbeing at the centre of lighting, planning and design processes, integrated within a wider decision making approach. Therefore the report is crafted to address a broad spectrum of target groups at policy level, specifically within municipalities.

POLICY MAKERS

Local government council members, mayors and city managers, policy advisors

THEIR ROLE

- Balancing diverse interests
- Managing limited resources and budgets
- Ensuring policy alignment with public welfare

WHAT THEY CAN EXPECT FROM THE GUIDELINES:

Methodologies and evidence-based insights to integrate wellbeing-oriented criteria into urban lighting policies, emphasising the benefits of well-designed lighting on residents' quality of life.

TECHNICAL AND MAINTENANCE DEPARTMENTS

Municipal civil servants and designers working in housing, environment, energy, public realm design and maintenance, safety and security and other departments that can directly or indirectly address urban lighting

THEIR ROLE

- Addressing technical and budgetary constraints
- Evolving technology standards
- Addressing safety needs and perception of safety
- Creating a welcoming and attractive public space at night

WHAT THEY CAN EXPECT FROM THE GUIDELINES:

Recommendations for lighting oriented to quality of life, showcasing innovative solutions and fostering cross-departmental collaboration to achieve optimal outcomes.

HEALTH, WELLBEING AND SOCIAL SERVICES DEPARTMENTS

Local health, wellbeing and social services local funders and providers, health professionals working with regional or state agencies, and social services staff supporting vulnerable populations and addressing social determinants of health.

THEIR ROLE

- Addressing public health needs
- Promoting social cohesion,
- Promoting health in all policies through integration of health considerations into urban development.

WHAT THEY CAN EXPECT FROM THE GUIDELINES:

Understanding the importance of integrating lighting into wellbeing and health policies, by offering insights into how well-designed lighting can improve social cohesion and public wellbeing.

SETTING

THE SCENE

WHAT ARE

WELLBEING AND HEALTH

IN URBAN LIGHTING?

URBAN LIGHTING

Urban lighting generally refers to artificial lighting for which cities are responsible through public policy and maintenance, and which can be set out in a lighting masterplan or lighting strategy, bringing together stakeholders, technologies, planners and designers for its development. Historically, urban lighting includes both permanent and temporary lighting. Even though the term urban lighting is used to mostly referred to outdoor spaces (e.g. street lighting, bike and pedestrian paths, architectural lighting) urban lighting is also partially part of the public realm (e.g. many urban indoor spaces are public and need to be lit as well).

WELLBEING

Wellbeing is a multidisciplinary concept found in both policy and everyday language. It generally connotes a multidimensional and holistic sense of having one's needs and aspirations met to a reasonable extent and includes both the feeling and the reality of being well and having a good 'quality of life'. Because of this multidimensionality, different people, policies and disciplines will include different elements under wellbeing. Amongst the most common dimensions of wellbeing are usually found: the meeting of basic needs (as defined by a particular culture); good health/

Defining a common ground and using a common language among different disciplines and expertise is a challenging task but is crucial in order to integrate health and wellbeing into lighting and other urban policies.

absence of debilitating disease; positive physical and social conditions that support social inclusion and the capacity to pursue individual and collective projects [1].

URBAN HEALTH

The study of urban health considers how characteristics of the urban environment may affect population health directly and indirectly, influencing what are typically considered risk factors for population health, such as thermal comfort, air quality, ventilation in buildings, etc. In the realm of urban healthy lighting, several interconnected domains must be considered to develop comprehensive policies [2].

The ENLIGHTENme common operational language is a structured framework designed to enhance communication and collaboration across the diverse disciplines engaged in the project. Given its multidisciplinary scope and the necessity for a transdisciplinary approach to lighting policies, this language standardises terminology and concepts, ensuring clarity and mutual understanding among researchers, stakeholders, and residents.

WHY

IS LIGHTING

IMPORTANT?

While the positive impacts of natural light on health are increasingly well-documented, with studies pointing to an association with mental health [3, 4, 5], improved sleep quality [6] and reduced risk of infectious diseases [7], there is a dearth of scientific research examining the effects of artificial light on health, particularly in relation to human behaviours and social interactions, which may be more widespread than currently acknowledged [8], [9], [10]. Research and practice has predominantly focused on the technical and aesthetic aspects of urban lighting, and safety and security concerns, potentially overlooking its implications for public health and wellbeing. However urban lighting can profoundly impact social goals, including fostering inclusion, equality, diversity, and overall quality of life.

Cities play a crucial role in shaping and supporting the health and wellbeing of most people worldwide. With more than half of the global population residing in urban areas (over 70% in Europe) the urban environment significantly influences the physical and mental wellbeing of individuals. Factors such as pollution levels, urban layout, availability of natural spaces, urban activities, and social patterns are recognised as urban determinants that impact people's quality of life. Among these urban determinants, artificial lighting, particularly outdoor lighting, has received limited attention.

QUALITY OF LIFE RATIONALE

'Quality of life' points to all aspects of living in a city, including the health and safety of residents and their wellbeing, as well as their ability to participate in the life of the city and to pursue the way of life they value. Lighting has a role in improving the quality of life of all residents and visitors to city space, inside and outside, public and private. These Guidelines are focused on this broad and inclusive sense of quality of life.

Lighting is often overlooked or assigned a minor importance in urban planning, yet it can play many different roles in improving and supporting quality of life, both directly and indirectly. In fact, its significance extends beyond mere illumination, influencing broader aspects of urban design and planning. Some of the key examples include:

- Inclusivity and aiding equity of access in terms of gender, age, ability and ethnicity;
- Mobility and safety, surveillance;
- Care in public indoor spaces;
- Zoning, integrating and negotiating co-presence
- Wayfinding, visibility, comfort;
- Energy efficiency.

ECONOMIC RATIONALE

Lighting is also about more than health and wellbeing – it is about economic development, nighttime regulation, city management, energy consumption and environmental costs. In terms of costs, the decision making process often includes a formal assessment of the costs and benefits, as well as the budgetary impact of investing in new lighting measures.

There is growing scientific evidence that optimizing outdoor and indoor lighting practices can result in significant cost savings for municipalities by improving energy efficiency, reducing maintenance expenses, and lowering healthcare-related expenditures [11], [12], [13], [14], [15].

This means it is important to identify the benefits associated with lighting; economists can then use various approaches to estimate the additional economic value of lighting and compare with the costs of implementation and ongoing maintenance.

In terms of the cost and benefits of lighting interventions, the impacts of artificial lighting on human health also have economic costs, particularly the adverse potential disruption of circadian rhythms [16], [17].

IMPORTANCE OF BRIDGING THE GAPS

Despite growing awareness of these issues, research on the effects of artificial lighting on the quality of life remains limited. The scarcity of research addressing the nexus between lighting and health and wellbeing outcomes on human beings is producing a knowledge gap which is reflected in urban policies, that have yet to fully address the health and wellbeing implications of artificial lighting.

This situation affects also interdisciplinary collaboration between urban planners, architects, health professionals, and lighting experts. Efforts to address these gaps at city level have to face several challenges and barriers, including:

- Limited awareness about the effects of artificial lighting on quality of life;
- Perception of lighting as a secondary issue;
- Focus on technical issues only;
- Lack of cross-sectoral integration;
- Lack of attention to cost efficiency of lighting related to health.

To this can be added increasing public concern with impacts of lighting on nature such as its implications for biodiversity. The increased knowledge of the impacts of outdoor artificial lighting that these Guidelines aim to show should be part of a comprehensive approach that recognize the interconnected health of humans, animals, and ecosystems in relation to urban lighting. This means to find a balance between urban needs nocturnal ecosystems and biodiversity protection by integrating holistic lighting solutions that address human health alongside environmental preservation.

ROLE OF LIGHTING

FOR QUALITY OF LIFE

Lighting plays a key role in enhancing the **QUALITY OF LIFE** for all residents and visitors, both indoors and outdoors, in public and private spaces

ROLES OF LIGHTING

Lighting promotes **INCLUSION, EQUALITY, and DIVERSITY** by reducing social isolation, fostering community engagement, and enhancing participation in social activities.

Lighting shapes **ATMOSPHERE**, supports **BIODIVERSITY**, and enhances **AMBIENCE** and meaning in heritage sites, green spaces, and urban areas.

MOST VULNERABLE GROUPS

CHILDREN

WOMEN

OLDER ADULTS

PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

Importance of **SAFETY** and **COMFORT** through well-illuminated pathways and gathering areas.

Optimized lighting reduces energy consumption, lowering costs and boosting **ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY**.

Lighting shapes **PUBLIC SPACES**, enhancing usability and ambiance across indoor, heritage, and green areas.

Improved lighting enhances **WAYFINDING** and supports **MOBILITY** by increasing visibility

MAIN POLICY INSTRUMENTS

FOR LIGHTING

TO ENHANCE QUALITY OF LIFE

Urban lighting is multifaceted and connects with a variety of policy instruments dealing with health, wellbeing, environmental sustainability, and economic efficiency: cities might use any or all of these to improve lighting for a better quality of life. **Urban lighting is not simply an aesthetic, technological or economic issue: consequently it should not be treated as a narrowly sectoral topic, and should rather be linked to wider urban and health related policies.**

REGULATORY INSTRUMENTS

They shape lighting policies through standards, codes, bans, and urban planning guidelines. Integrating health and wellbeing considerations can enhance urban lighting quality. Standards and codes ensure consistency and safety, while driving the transition to more energy-efficient and ecological lighting solutions. In some settings, particularly for major infrastructure projects with substantial budgetary impact, there may be legal requirements for formal impact assessments for public investments, including lighting. These assessments can incorporate health impacts, and gathering evidence on lighting's cross-sector benefits strengthens its case in the assessment process.

ECONOMIC INSTRUMENTS

These instruments may play a crucial role in incentivising and supporting the adoption of a health-sensitive perspective of lighting. Taxes and subsidies are frequently used to encourage the use of energy-efficient lighting technologies by making them more financially accessible. Market-based instruments, such as tradable permits or certificates for low-emission lighting, create economic incentives for reducing light pollution and energy consumption. Public procurement policies ensure that government agencies lead by example in adopting sustainable lighting solutions, while research and development (R&D) support fosters innovation in lighting technologies and health-focused design. However, these economic tools in most cases do not focus on health and wellbeing and more generally on the quality of life, even though they facilitate the transition to better lighting in ecological terms, but also stimulate market growth and technological advancements.

INFORMATIONAL INSTRUMENTS

These instruments comprise labels and certifications that would inform consumers and businesses identifying lighting products that meet specific standards ensuring transparency and can be influenced with specific elements related to correct lighting. Public awareness campaigns might educate residents about the importance of correctly illuminating their homes and encourage behaviours that support it, such as using appropriate light levels, reducing unnecessary lighting. By leveraging these informational tools, policymakers would effectively engage the public and private sectors in the collective effort to improve urban lighting.

STRATEGIES AND FRAMEWORKS

Strategic documents like lighting masterplans should provide comprehensive guidelines for urban lighting within a city or region, addressing various aspects of lighting design, implementation, and management. These plans aim to enhance the nighttime environment while minimising energy consumption and negative impacts on ecosystems and human health, fostering balanced lighting solutions that meet the diverse needs of communities while promoting sustainability. Urban planning and infrastructure guidelines, along with masterplans, provide a strategic framework for deploying these solutions systematically across the city, while smart city initiatives leverage technology to enhance lighting management and efficacy.

Economic development and investment strategies, including the nighttime economy, and strategies targeting specific demographics (e.g., related to gender safety and equality, active ageing, and youth) involve lighting-related decisions and opportunities insofar as they all involve producing appropriate public and private indoor and outdoor spaces.

These policy instruments refer to and are managed at different institutional levels—local, regional, national or international—each with tailored instruments, strategies and roles.

At the **local level**, implementation typically involves a combination of regulatory frameworks, zoning rules, building codes, and public-private partnerships etc. These policies are often integrated with or connected to broader urban policies such as sustainable development strategies, climate action plans, and urban revitalisation initiatives.

Regional initiatives further reinforce efforts to promote responsible lighting design and minimise the ecological impact of artificial light. Quite a few regions also have the remit of developing and pursuing health and wellbeing strategies or take care of setting higher standards than the national level for reducing impacts on the environment due to artificial lighting.

At the **national level**, governments may implement overarching strategies and regulations to guide urban lighting policies across the country. For instance, national policies could include setting standards for lighting efficiency and quality, establishing incentives or subsidies for municipalities to adopt sustainable lighting practices, or funding research and development initiatives to advance lighting technologies. National governments might also enact legislation to regulate light pollution and ensure that urban lighting projects align with broader environmental and public health goals.

Even though there are no binding obligations set at international level concerning urban lighting, the European Commission and other international and intergovernmental organisations might play a key role in stimulating governments to think more holistically about lighting and how it impacts people's quality of life, supporting research and observatories to generate data and inform conscious strategies. At the same time international institutions dealing with health, may consider lighting more clearly as a urban determinant of health and wellbeing in cities.

SHARING

THE VISION

AT CITY LEVEL

SHARING THE VISION

AT CITY LEVEL

If cities want to give lighting a more integrated role in policies and practices for contributing to improve people's quality of life and wellbeing, it is crucial to put this urban component high in cities' agendas by considering the following actions.

THE IMPORTANCE OF ESTABLISHING A MULTIDISCIPLINARY TEAM

Lighting policies and interventions at urban level can be hampered by a siloed approach hindering effective communication and commitment across different city departments that may have very different interests and objectives. Hence, to address lighting as a complex and multifaceted issue able to play a key role in supporting wellbeing and quality of life of people it is important firstly to take relevant expertise on board by establishing a **multi-disciplinary team** within the locality, and then engage with local stakeholders across multiple sectors tailoring the communication to their expertise. Multiple policy makers with separate budgets from different sectors may potentially have a role to play in developing good lighting policy.

These policy makers may set the strategic framework, and determine the extent to which health and wellbeing issues are integrated in lighting policies. At policy level, the team should include various expertise including urban planning, lighting, engineering, public works, public health and wellbeing, social services, police and safety, and justice, marketing teams, digital development planning, nighttime economy and entertainment officers and additional experts on secondment. All this involves actors who have or represent interests in enhancing peoples' quality of life through lighting planning and design. Being able to start a lighting master planning process within an urban design group that includes

these representatives allows lighting to be designed within the full range of city policy and development planning – and for it to contribute to city development in ways that the individual non-lighting departments would not imagine [18].

THE IMPORTANCE OF BUILDING A COMMON GROUND AND COMMON LANGUAGE

Silos can be strong barriers not only in terms of practice but also in terms of mentality and approaches across different disciplines and domains. Capacity building activities are fundamental to support the creation of awareness and promote knowledge sharing at the local level. To better understand the health and wellbeing implications of different policies, individuals who have responsibility for health promotion and public health policy in the city are critical in improving knowledge and capacities within the city departments.

Training programmes are important tools to achieve this goal: the healthy city management approach (HCM) [19] aims to stimulate the coordination of public policies based on studying and monitoring health determinants through an innovative transdisciplinary, multistakeholder and multilevel method within public administrations [20]. The training programme aims to put this topic on the agenda of decision makers and key stakeholders, including those working in the lighting and urban planning domain. Moreover, it contributes to broadening awareness of population and local services and NGOs that deal with the themes of wellbeing.

The first edition of the HCM training in Bologna organized within ENLIGHTENme (© Chiara Spinato)

ENLIGHTENme Healthy City Manager Training Program

The Healthy City Manager Training Program is a 100-hour course promoted by the National Association of Italian Municipalities and the Ministry of Youth in Italy. It is designed for participants under 35, with a total of 250 trainees, each completing a 100-hour course. The initiative trains city officials to integrate health into urban planning, environment, housing, and transportation. Participants, including urban planners and social service professionals, are engaged in interactive sessions to reduce inequalities and foster healthier cities. Inspired by WHO principles, the program addressed social, economic, and cultural barriers while promoting policy alignment and participation. Real-world case studies and scenario exercises helped participants navigating political challenges, build community

trust, and implement long-term monitoring. Following the course, several Italian cities, including Turin, Bologna, Bari, Bergamo, Imola, and Sanluri, hosted trained Health City Managers (HCMs) for job experiences. Additionally, Genoa and Palermo appointed two professionals to take on the role of HCMs. The ENLIGHTENme project also developed a condensed version of the training, delivered in two editions across the three pilot cities: Amsterdam, Bologna, and Tartu.

THE IMPORTANCE OF A MULTILEVEL APPROACH

Local authorities deal with lighting at several different levels and in different phases, each involving different ways of organising people and processes:

- **Planning:** Cities adopt a planning approach to lighting urban development plans, master plans and urban design guidelines, heritage and economic development strategies, mobility plans are some examples. As far as lighting is concerned, some cities have bespoke lighting master plans; others integrate lighting within city-wide planning and design strategies instead. Additionally, there are other policy initiatives and departments concerned with service provision – policing, safety, sustainability, social care – that are not planning focused but take important lighting-related strategic decisions.

- **Projects:** Cities have to renew lighting and lighting systems at city-wide, district and local level. Moreover, lighting is a necessary component in urban projects – from street level renovations, through public space designs, commercial centres to district-wide rezoning and development. Lighting has to be designed if cities want to place quality of life, wellbeing and health centrally in their wider planning and design processes, and this needs to be appropriate to specific projects and localities, as well as compliant with city-wide policies. Therefore it is important to engage lighting designers in the early stages of the project since they can positively contribute to gather information about the space, its social and cultural context, its functions and its users, before the design process begin.
- **Maintenance and operational control:** Once installed, cities generally regard lighting as the responsibility of a lighting unit or department, limited to repair, testing and maintenance unless specific issues call for renovation.

This is problematic for two reasons:

- Findings show that responsive and effective maintenance of lighting is more important to residents than design: it is crucial in mediating their relationship with the city, colouring their entire view of their status as residents on a daily basis.
- Lighting technologies (e.g. control systems, dimming schedules, tunable colour temperatures, 'smart') are increasingly adaptable: lighting is no longer simply an infrastructure to be maintained in a steady state over decades. Lighting can now be seen as ongoing area of city intervention, monitoring and innovation.

MAKING THE ECONOMIC CASE FOR INVESTMENTS IN OUTDOOR AND INDOOR LIGHTING

The importance of good light exposure is not typically highlighted as a major public health or broader economic priority. One of the reasons may be because there is limited awareness of potential adverse economic impacts of poor lighting. There appear to be very few cost effectiveness studies that have looked at the case for good lighting, particularly as an intervention to improve and protect health and wellbeing.

However, as mentioned before, poor light exposure is associated with multiple adverse impacts within and beyond health systems (e.g. effects on circadian rhythm disruption and perception spaces that reduces the sense of community and intergenerational connections), all of which have economic costs. Identifying these impacts can help strengthen the case for investing in good lighting. For instance, the annual economic costs of poor sleep have been estimated at almost 2% of economic output (GDP) in both Germany and the UK. If poor lighting hampers social connections it may also increase the risk of loneliness. In Spain the annual costs of loneliness for the population have been estimated to be more than 1.2% of GDP (€14 billion in 2021), and work in England indicates that modest reductions in loneliness through better community engagement can be cost effective [21][22].

Therefore, if investment in effective lighting interventions can reduce even just a small fraction of these costs they are likely to be very cost effective.

How to strengthen the economic case for investing in lighting interventions?

A first critical step is to identify the potential costs associated with not taking action to improve access to good light exposure. Many data are available on the costs to health care systems and society of living with different conditions, such as depression or anxiety. Information on both short and longer terms costs of these conditions can be collated, and the potential economic benefits of even a small reduction in risk calculated.

In addition to health-based economic cases, the economic impacts of good lighting can clearly be assessed in terms of:

- nighttime economy – both increased consumption and entertainment and economically beneficial impacts on nighttime workers
- savings on policing and criminal justice systems from more effective public safety, often due to increased social participation
- attraction of investment both within the city and in surrounding areas as people and businesses are attracted to more welcoming environment.

For a lighting intervention to have a good economic case, it should be stressed that it does not need to 'save money'. Many policy actions, certainly in health sector, will increase costs but at the same time improve outcomes. Different methods of economic evaluation can be used to compare the relative costs and benefits of two or more policy choices. The two most useful are cost benefit analysis and cost utility analysis.

Currently there is very limited evidence on the cost effectiveness of different indoor and outdoor lighting interventions. One way to increase the evidence base is to work with economists to build decision models to estimate the potential economic case of investment. This approach is widely used in health economics and brings together existing evidence on effectiveness of lighting interventions with information on their costs.

LIGHTING

YOUR CITY,

A STRATEGIC

APPROACH

LIGHTING YOUR CITY,

A STRATEGIC

APPROACH

This section outlines a practical and strategic approach to lighting that integrates it within wider city design and planning, and targets it on quality of life of diverse users of urban space. ‘Good lighting’ depends on bringing together relevant stakeholders – both city professionals and citizens – to produce real understanding of the diverse public space needs of different urban actors and to respond creatively to meet them. The aim is to generate city-specific social knowledge and design options instead of relying on compliance with generalized standards.

Lighting is – or should be – a complicated matter for cities because it cannot be treated in isolation as a purely technical or engineering matter. In any public space that a city needs to manage, lighting:

- interacts with different kinds of people, with different aims, relationships, activities, values and cultures;
- interacts with a huge range of other spatial and design features such as the layout of streets, traffic patterns, material such as pavements or paints, private lighting sources such as shops;
- involves rapidly changing technologies that connect it to control systems, digital surveillance and data production and wider infrastructure;
- interacts with governmental and regulatory structures, policies, departments, when it comes to its management. In the case of ENLIGHTENme, lighting for elderly quality of life directly involves understanding of ageing policy, social care systems, mobility regulations and so on.

Because good lighting depends on bringing together so many connections, a strategic approach needs to be both **multidisciplinary** and **integrated** within wider urban governance. Good lighting requires meaningful communication between:

- Social and economic expertise, including expertise in evaluation,
- Spatial planning and design expertise,
- Technical expertise,
- Governmental and policy expertise.

More than this, integrating lighting within urban governance should ideally be an **iterative process**. All of this expertise needs to be developed through all stages of lighting management, from design through post-implementation assessment. In ENLIGHTENme for example, social research needed to be more than baseline (pre-project) fact-finding; new lighting installations change public spaces in unpredictable ways, generating both new opportunities

and problems that need more research for effective urban management for wellbeing.

Therefore, these Guidelines offer an ideal strategy that comprises four clear components that were the focus of ENLIGHTENme research:

- Mapping to support design and planning;
- Social research and co-design;
- Public and community engagement;
- Prototyping, piloting, demonstrations, experimentations and continuing development.

To the extent that at least elements of these components are integrated into public space design and planning, the result will be ‘better lighting’ that addresses diverse needs of urban stakeholders.

PRODUCING DATA TO SUPPORT LIGHTING DESIGN AND PLANNING

Cities already generate enormous amounts of data that can be drawn into lighting policy and planning in ways that will integrate them in an evidence-based manner into wider city strategies, planning and prioritization. This is another strong argument in favour of a multidisciplinary team-based approach to lighting.

Three major areas of urban data can be considered, providing baseline material for mainstreaming lighting within urban planning:

Socio-economic and urban conditions: collecting data across the city on relative vulnerabilities, marginalised populations, hotspots for social problems such as crime, inaccessibility, lack of amenities, etc, can help to identify and prioritise districts where lighting investment are more likely to support vulnerable populations.

Lighting data: conversely, lighting departments have significant data to share concerning location and specifications of lighting infrastructure that can be integrated

more closely with city data on crime, health, inclusion, mobility and so on. Crucially, lighting data can contribute to defining very important but generally overlooked indicators of urban vulnerabilities: careful lighting measurements can point out unequal access to sunlight that indicate wider urban deprivations such as lighting obstructions (such as trees or hoardings) that indicate issues of maintenance or bad planning for citizen wellbeing.

Health and wellbeing data: lighting is rarely connected directly to health data, including not only illness and mortality data but also data on injuries, falls and mental health. Even less available and integrated is data that sheds light on wider wellbeing, activity levels, social networks, hobbies and sports. Cities could not only work to integrate health and wellbeing data but also to promote creativity in producing new measures that would support public space policy.

The ENLIGHTENme project developed a WebGIS-based Urban Lighting and Health multiscale platform, structured into three levels: a global open ATLAS of best practices, city-level urban lighting and health maps, and district-level 3D models of target areas. The maps created for the three ENLIGHTENme cities—Bologna, Amsterdam, and Tartu—visualize indicators and correlations across socio-economic determinants, urban lighting patterns, satellite-detected lighting, and population health and wellbeing, which are combined to provide vulnerability maps and index. These maps supported the identification of most deprived districts for targeted interventions.

(Vulnerability Index maps: <https://appweenlightenmep01.azurewebsites.net/>)

SOCIAL RESEARCH AND CO-DESIGN

Cities can develop an understanding of diverse population needs through a combination of social research, community engagement and co-design. The aim is to efficiently identify, engage and understand the different people who will use the spaces to be lit, their specific needs, aspirations, identities and interrelationships. It follows that this approach starts from site-specific research and design, working with particular people on particular places. Clearly, as discussed, cities need to operate on many levels, from small projects to city wide masterplanning. However, the focus in these Guidelines is to start from knowledge of actual people and places and then see how findings and solutions can be generalised to larger scales.

Social research

It is important to develop research that identifies the kinds of people that use public spaces and those who do *not* use it but would want to. Social research for good lighting involves reaching out and working with those social groups to understand their needs and issues, and more generally their actual or potential relationship to the spaces in question.

- **Purposes and practices:** what do people want to do in this place? What role does this place play in their wider journeys and practices (getting to work, going shopping, leisure activities)? In what ways does this space support or hinder their desired uses?
- **Understanding public space:** different social groups understand and value (and fear) public spaces in radically different ways that need to be brought to light, particularly in multicultural and diverse cities. Public space involves different issues and meanings, for example, for women of different ages, different ethnicities, teenagers, and so on. Lighting public spaces needs to connect with how different social groups understand the very idea of public space.
- **Social connection, participation and access:** in what ways does this place foster or hinder social participation? what are the drivers and barriers generating social isolation/exclusion of vulnerable groups?

- **Sharing spaces, identity and ownership:** any urban lit space is a shared space, a space of co-presence of very diverse people. Who feels comfortable in this space and has a sense of ownership? who doesn't? How do people narrate and describe this space in terms of its history, meaning, problems, safety?

Socio-spatial analysis

Social research needs to be carefully connected to a material understanding of the space itself. This can start from both data provided by the city and the issues raised by social research, and needs to explore the relationship between users of the space and its material organization. More concretely, what are the paths most frequently used by different people in their routine practices? How do these relate to fixed features such as lighting and landscaping? How does the spatial organization of the place change over day and night, the week, the seasons?

(Photo © LSE-CL)

Tools

ENLIGHTENme used a range of research tools for both social research and spatial analysis [23] [24] [25]:

- **Semi-structured interviews** with stakeholders, including both extensive interviews and brief informal conversations;
- **“Walkabouts”** and other in-situ observation and discussion of local settings, including installation sites;
- Observation and photo/video documentation of neighbourhoods and installation sites, in different days of the week, seasons and times of the day;
- **Workshops** with participants in the different stages of the design process;
- **Participation in meetings** and activities of a range of local organisations.

PUBLIC AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT – MAKING LIGHTING PART OF WIDER PLANNING AND DESIGN

The co-design process is based on the identification of relevant stakeholders to be brought on board. The network of stakeholders at the local level includes those who might be involved or affected by lighting design and projects. The following groups of stakeholders represent a relevant sample to consider.

- **Vulnerable groups** including socially and economically active stakeholders, of different living conditions, with or without disabilities;
- **Care provision departments** including hospitals, churches, social workers, night economy workers, medical care professionals, teachers, maintenance personnel, custodians, physiotherapist, etc.;
- **Local organisations** including community centres, outreach programs, libraries, city-level activists, and charity groups working on age or urban design issues;
- **Civil society living** in the area which might have a stake in the development of new lighting design;

Urban Lighting Labs were set up in Amsterdam, Bologna, and Tartu to address urban, lighting, and socio-economic vulnerabilities. They brought together older adults, caregivers, policymakers, designers, and local organizations, serving as hubs for social research, co-design workshops, and consultation during lighting installations. Lighting trials and demonstrations ensured continuous community engagement through iterative experiments with dimming and color temperature settings.

(Photo © LSE-CL)

- **Commercial organisations** gravitating around the place.

Local organisations have substantial influence due to their community involvement and advocacy, therefore their interest may vary depending on how directly urban lighting affects their specific goals. Keeping them satisfied ensures their support and prevents potential opposition. The vulnerable groups are highly interested in urban lighting as it affects their safety, accessibility, and quality of life. However, they typically have less direct power to influence policies. Keeping them informed and engaged ensures that their needs are considered in the decision-making process. Carers are deeply invested in the wellbeing of vulnerable groups, making them highly interested in urban lighting outcomes.

The multi-level and multi-stakeholder interactions:

- 1 **Policy makers ↔ Vulnerable groups & Carers:** policy makers actively involve the vulnerable groups and carers in the consultation process to ensure their needs and concerns are addressed.
- 2 **Technical Departments ↔ Policy makers:** Both groups collaborate closely on the technical and design aspects of urban lighting projects.
- 3 **Health and Social Services Professionals ↔ Vulnerable groups & Carers:** These professionals advocate for the health and wellbeing of the vulnerable groups and carers, ensuring that lighting policies support their needs.
- 4 **Technical Departments ↔ Local Organisations:** Technical departments may collaborate with local organizations on specific technical aspects or to address community concerns.
- 5 **Health and Social Services Professionals ↔ Local Organisations:** Health and social services professionals work with local organisations to promote initiatives that improve public health and wellbeing.

How?

- Not just workshops, but inclusion of care provision departments and organisations, commercial organisations, civil society – depending on aims of the policy or project
- Emphasise strong overlap with social research and lighting (and urban) design development
- Engagement includes ensuring that there are multiple and meaningful forums for discussion and dispute, for making public the aims, needs and values of different stakeholders in planning and designing their spaces.

They have limited direct power but can be influential through advocacy and support. Keeping them informed helps ensure their concerns are addressed.

The collaborative work that is carried out at a local level sees an interest and involvement at a decision-making and political level by those expertises who are put to collaborate through the multidisciplinary team, making the development of integrated and shared lighting solutions a multi-level and multi-stakeholder process.

The outcomes of public and community engagement can either produce recommendations about lighting settings (e.g. dimming after a curfew time, adjusting specific colour temperature) or highlight variations that city lighting policy must address (e.g. colour temperature is impacting visual confusion, but desired temperatures vary by ethnic, class, gender, disability or others that need to be investigated during the lighting design process).

PROTOTYPING, PILOTING, DEMONSTRATIONS, EXPERIMENTATION AND CONTINUING DEVELOPMENT

Experiment with unconventional approaches

The old stereotype of public lighting is of an engineering-driven process governed by top-down standards and cost constraints. With older technologies, the result has been once and for all installations that procure lighting for periods of 20-30 years. New lighting and control technologies, coupled with different forms of city organisation, community engagement and design practices should make this inflexibility a thing of the past. We can envisage city lighting as an ongoing, iterative and responsive process. It opens the possibility to also use small installations as test-beds or laboratories so that both residents, designers and cities can properly and intelligently experience and experiment with design options. Public and interactive activities should include a sufficient number of stakeholders to significantly represent the key demographic variables for the intervention

In Europe there is some convergence around light settings: 3000k and moderate brightness. However, these are features that need to be explored for implementing any lighting strategy, since both brightness levels and Colour Temperature are perceived differently according to cultural differences, that will give residents different feelings of comfort/discomfort.

From ENLIGHTENme experimentations, it has been demonstrated that much lower levels of brightness and colour temperature are acceptable and can be adopted over time. As people learn about and experience different light qualities, more and more options open up for design, while more adaptive technologies allow experimentation, as well as the ability to vary lighting qualities across times of day, week and season.

(Sketches © Argun Paragamyam)

context. Instruments that are helpful for tailoring light to the needs of the people:

- Lighting systems that can be controlled by mobile app to enable real time adjustments to light levels and colour temperature;
- Use of public events in the installation site to involve and educate a wider public in lighting and public space. Activities designed to 'materialise' design options, including lighting so that people can experience them (not just citizens but technical and planning personnel).

Several lighting parameters may influence the choices and lifestyles of people: brightness level/dimming, uniformity, and colour temperature and colour rendering index. The experiments with global settings of these two lighting allow to understand social dynamics and changes in the use and perception of public spaces.

Lighting systems that are capable of adjusting brightness, colour temperature, operational schedules, and more, provide cities with powerful tools to balance energy efficiency, safety, and quality of life.

Proposed organization for experimenting

A first series of workshops and night walks should be aimed at raising awareness and interest in the installation, also exploring dimming and colour temperature to help people articulate responses to lighting and atmosphere. A second series of workshops will serve to assess awareness and experience of lighting settings, or to replicate the experiments. Start discussing the future plans for the installations. A final series of workshops could be organised to assess and discuss experiences of lighting. Semi-structured interviews with participants representing key demographics for the area should focus on assessing participants' experience of the sites.

Monitoring, assessment and experimentations

Monitoring and assessment play a pivotal role in ensuring the effectiveness and sustainability of urban lighting projects. This involves systematically tracking the use of public spaces and social interactions, allowing for adjustments to lighting configurations based on observed patterns and needs. Additionally, monitoring lighting-related metrics, such as energy costs, provides valuable insights into the project's environmental and economic impact. Regular feedback mechanisms, involving input from stakeholders and community members, facilitate ongoing improvement and revision of lighting strategies. By integrating comprehensive monitoring and assessment protocols, urban lighting initiatives can continuously evolve to meet the needs of residents while minimising environmental impact and optimising resource utilisation.

Data gathered from smart lighting systems can play a pivotal role. At present, these data gathered from these systems remains underutilized. There is a need for stronger data-sharing agreements between lighting companies and municipalities, allowing insights from real-world installations to inform future policies and designs.

Adaptive lighting systems were implemented in Bologna, Amsterdam, and Tartu as part of the ENLIGHTENme project. In Bologna, dynamic LED lanterns and projectors ensure uniform lighting, enhancing safety and comfort by adjusting light flux and color temperature. A multi-head pole with adjustable spotlights in a gathering area allows users to modify lighting for different events. Amsterdam integrated tunable white LEDs into a bridge handrail, improving safety for pedestrians and cyclists while transforming the bridge into a nighttime landmark. The system allows adjustments in brightness and color temperature to suit various conditions and aesthetics. In Tartu, adaptive LED lighting in bridge handrails optimizes visibility while preventing glare. RGBW projectors at the bridge's base create dynamic lighting effects, while multi-head poles at the lakeside beach offer adjustable lighting to support seasonal recreational activities.

A BETTER LIGHT

FOR A GOOD

QUALITY

OF LIFE

A BETTER LIGHT

FOR A GOOD

QUALITY OF LIFE:

GENERAL RECOMMENDATIONS

1

Adopt an holistic approach for (all) lighting interventions overcoming standardized parameters and 1-solution-fits-all approaches

Lighting should not be treated separately from the social practices and social spaces that are to be lit. A good lighting design is one that responds to people's needs and supports the activities that residents consider important in the specific public space. Adopting a holistic approach to lighting design means to stop framing it as solely an engineering-based matter, instead integrating it with other urban features of the public space that make it usable by people: benches, accesses, entrance routes, reduction of visual and other sensory confusion. Good lighting starts from analysis of the intervention site, the social structure of its users and the relationship between them. Understanding the determinants for people's wellbeing is the priority and it is more important than relying on codified lighting levels recommendations determined a priori.

2

Integrate community support networks into public space design, including lighting

Experimentations carried out with groups of older people within the ENLIGHTENme project highlighted the need to connect the lighting domain to social care provision, community support networks, urban design and public space management. These findings suggest overcoming the sectoral approach, instead including different actors belonging to the social services departments and community support network into holistic public space design processes, which include also lighting aspects. This will lead to the design of inclusive, vibrant public spaces accessible by all, not forgetting the most vulnerable groups.

3

Designing light for inclusive public spaces

Public space lighting is analysed by people in terms of **functionality** and **aesthetics** and **atmosphere**. Both have a huge impact on public space use, and generally operate together to make a sense of being 'comfortable'. Moreover, there is a variability of both night and light across seasons. In particular, the coincidence of darkness and dinner time in different seasons leads to different lighting needs, and opportunity for artificial lighting to support access to public space during more of the day.

A more uniformly distributed light (that is, without bright and dark patches) is rated as more comfortable and more safe.

5

Break down functional fragmentation towards more inclusive lighting interventions

Lighting design is notoriously split into functional specialisms, providing design criteria that differ from outdoor to indoor lighting, residential to commercial to civic, etc. However, experimentations coming from ENLIGHTENme project demonstrate that taking the perspective of the wellbeing of older people requires breaking down that functional fragmentation and working from the actual life and spatial practices of different sorts of older people.

4

Embracing differences, planning for complexity and adaptability

Residents have different meanings and uses of public spaces, different experiences of safety, security and comfort and discomfort. Be prepared to embrace differences to enhance the quality of lighting. Cities need to make spaces that are 'good' for diverse residents who share (or fail to share) public spaces. Using lighting to create different feelings of spaces, or to fit the needs of some residents and not others, is part of making the city public for all. Define smart lighting systems allow for much more dynamic variation and response to needs of different residents at different times of day, week and year. It is not required setting levels across a site and at all times to accommodate specific needs, but it does require cities to do the kind of *site-specific* research that can adjust relevant spaces and times for these needs.

HEALTH & URBAN LIGHTING

ADVISORY BOARD

The **Health & Urban Lighting Advisory Board (HULAB)** was established within the ENLIGHTENme project to explore the intersection of urban lighting, health, and wellbeing.

All through the project, HULAB acted as a working group to advise on innovative and sustainable principles for connecting lighting policies with citizen health and wellbeing.

Led by **LUCI**, and chaired by the City of London Corporation, **HULAB** brought together 16 cities—alongside the project's three pilot cities (Amsterdam, Bologna and Tartu)—to provide expert guidance on sustainable and health-conscious urban lighting strategies.

HULAB's mission was to ensure that urban lighting policies not only enhance safety and functionality but also support citizens' sleep-wake cycles, promote active lifestyles, and foster social interaction. By sharing best practices, research, and practical recommendations, HULAB helped shape innovative approaches to lighting master planning.

Landmark initiatives include the **HULAB Lighting Masterplan series**, which examined how cities develop urban lighting policies and provided

insights into the processes, stakeholders, and health considerations involved. Ultimately, these efforts supported the drafting for the document you now hold in your hands, a key outcome of the ENLIGHTENme project.

HULAB was responsible for co-writing one of the chapters of the **LUCI Declaration for the Future of Urban Lighting**, embedding health and wellbeing as a fundamental goal for urban lighting worldwide.

Through collaboration and knowledge-sharing, HULAB and LUCI continue to advocate for lighting as a positive force for urban health and wellbeing, guiding cities toward a more sustainable and human-centric future.

Cities that participated in the HULAB initiative:

Albertslund (DK); Amsterdam (NL); Bologna (IT); Brasov (RO); Cascais, Guimarães (PT); Glasgow, City of London Corporation (UK); Larissa (GR); Leipzig (DE); Montpellier (FR); Oulu (FI); Philadelphia (USA); Ravenna, Reggio Emilia (IT); Seoul (KR); Stavanger (NO); Tallin (EE) and Tartu (EE).

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DISCLAIMER

The current guidelines report has been developed within the framework of the EU Horizon 2020 ENLIGHTENme project: Innovative policies for improving citizens' health and wellbeing addressing indoor and outdoor lighting.

It represents the result of a collaborative work involving 22 partners from different EU and non EU countries.

It aims to advance the understanding of how indoor and outdoor lighting affects health and wellbeing, particularly in elderly populations. It will develop innovative, evidence-based guidelines and policies for measures, technologies, and interventions that can be implemented with a dedicated Decision Support System to help both citizens and city leaders improve public health and wellbeing.

The ENLIGHTENme project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 945238.

The author is solely responsible for its content, it does not represent the opinion of the European Commission and the Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of data appearing therein.

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Printed by:
Imprimerie du Pont de Claix

ISBN:
978-2-9538201-6-4

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URBAN LIGHTING FOR HEALTH & WELLBEING: NEW GUIDELINES

In cities worldwide, urban lighting is a powerful determinant of public health. With more than half of the global population residing in urban areas (over 70% in Europe) the urban environment significantly influences the physical and mental wellbeing of individuals.

These guidelines aim to empower lighting professionals, city representatives, and researchers to advocate for and implement evidence-based lighting strategies that create healthier urban environments.

Navigate the complexities of urban lighting and build cities that prioritize human health and wellbeing.

Funded by
the European Union